

Hydrogen reduction of lumpy Nchwaning ore in a fixed bed reactor

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ABSTRACT: The application of hydrogen gas for prereduction of manganese ore may substitute fossil carbon consumption and as such reduce CO₂ emissions in manganese ferroalloy production. The pre-reduction behavior of Nchwaning manganese ore was investigated using a fixed bed reactor. Reduction rates at different temperatures and temperature programs were investigated, and particles were sieved after reduction to measure decrepitation. The reduction rate was measured by adding a tracer gas to the reducing gas and quantifying the off-gas by GC-analysis. Different particle size distributions of the input material were reduced to investigate the effect of particle size on reduction rate. Chemical analysis and XRD were used to characterize the raw and reduced material. The influence of particle size distribution and temperature on the oxygen removal rate are discussed. The manganese oxides were mostly reduced to MnO in the samples, while some iron oxide and carbonates remained. The reduction degree is improved by smaller particles and increased temperature.

Keywords: Manganese ore, reduction, hydrogen, decrepitation, particle size

1. Introduction

Manganese ferroalloys are mostly produced in submerged arc furnaces (SAF) where solid carbon reacts with MnO to produce manganese metal and CO gas, and CO gas reacts with the higher manganese and iron oxides ([Mn,Fe]O_x, x>1), albeit with some excess carbon consumption due to imperfect reduction of the higher oxides. The use of hydrogen in manganese ferroalloy production has been suggested to alleviate the carbon footprint of the product, and hydrogen has been shown to improve the prereduction of higher manganese and iron oxides compared to CO [1–5]. It is not practically feasible to produce manganese metal by neither H₂ nor CO [6–8], hence H₂ alone cannot fully displace all the carbon for reduction to metal. Recently, the HalMan process was suggested as a sustainable way of producing manganese alloys through hydrogen prereduction followed by aluminothermic reduction of MnO [9]. This process may reduce CO₂ emissions for manganese ferroalloy production depending on the CO₂ associated with the aluminium source.

The complete pre-reduction of manganese oxides can be described by reaction (1), using either H₂ or CO as a reductant. The final reduction of MnO to metal is described in reaction (2) for C or Al as a reductant. The higher iron oxides can be reduced similarly as the manganese oxides (reaction (1)), however it is possible to reduce iron oxides to metal by CO or H₂.

If the consumption of aluminium in the final reduction process is to be kept at a minimum, it is necessary to fully reduce the higher manganese oxides to MnO. Incomplete pre-reduction (reaction (1)) will result in additional oxygen that must be removed by increased consumption of the solid reductant (reaction (2)). The aluminium consumption may be further reduced if the iron oxides are reduced to metallic Fe by H₂. The reduction of the FeO in manganese ores is retarded by the reduced activity of iron oxides when in solid solution with manganese oxides [4,10–12], however, the formation of metallic iron has been observed during pre-reduction of manganese ores using pure H₂ [1,13,14].

In Fig. 1, the oxygen partial pressure of the manganese oxides and iron oxides are given as a function of temperature. In addition, the oxygen partial pressure of selected H₂/H₂O gas mixtures has been superimposed on the figure. It can be seen that if exposed to H₂/H₂O gas mixtures in the range 70-99% H₂, MnO is the stable manganese oxide, while in the Fe-O system, metallic iron is stable above about 550 °C if the H₂ content is 80 % and higher. With 70 % H₂ Fe₂O₃, FeO or Fe is stable depending on the temperature.

Fig. 1: Phase diagram for the Mn-O (black lines) and the Fe-O systems. The figure shows the stability of phases as function of temperature and oxygen partial pressure. The green lines denote the oxygen partial pressure of different H₂/H₂O gas mixtures. The H₂ content is given in the figure legend. Calculated using HSC Chemistry 10®.

The reactivity of manganese ores during gaseous reduction has been studied extensively [1,4,5,10,13,15–21], and factors such as temperature, ore type, reducing gas composition and particle size influence the reactivity of the ores during reduction. Reducing manganese ores in CO/CO₂/H₂ gas mixtures has been shown to increase the reaction rate by 20-30 % compared to CO/CO₂ gas mixtures with the same oxygen partial pressure [5]. Addition of H₂O to CO/CO₂ gas mixtures has also been seen to promote reduction of manganese ore due to production of H₂ in the water-gas shift reaction (H₂O+CO=H₂+CO₂) [3]. The reduction rate improves in the presence of H₂ due to its improved diffusion properties compared to CO and CO₂ [4], hence, the mass transfer of gas is important in the reduction of lumpy ores.

The presence of H₂O during reduction will shift the equilibrium of the chemical reaction (i.e. equation 1) hence reducing the driving force as the H₂O concentrations increase, as seen in fig. 1. During reduction of pyrolusite fines (<0.22 mm) at 375 °C, 1 % and 10 % addition of H₂O to H₂ reducing gas was seen to reduce the reaction rate by about 45 % and 75 %, respectively [21]. Under isothermal reduction of Nchwani ore in the temperature range 700-900 °C, the reaction rate was seen to increase by 60 % when changing the reducing atmosphere from 70 % H₂/30 % H₂O to 100 % H₂ [14]. The formation of metallic iron was observed during isothermal reduction of manganese ores between 700-900 °C in 100 % H₂, however it did not occur during reduction in 70 % H₂/30 % H₂O gas mixtures for the same ores [1,14]. Metallic iron formation has been observed during reduction in 100 %

H₂ down to 600 °C [20].

The reduction of manganese ores have been described by various different models, such as the shrinking core model [21], crackling core model [22], first order reaction [16], random nucleation and growth [23] and second order reaction [20,24]. Manganese ores vary based on factors such as mineral composition and porosity [15,25], and different studies have investigated wide ranges of particle sizes, both which may explain the differences in reduction behavior between the studies. Another possible source of the observed difference is the exothermic nature of the reactions between higher manganese oxides with H₂. The reduction reactions with H₂ and the enthalpy of reaction is given in equations 3, 4 and 5. Various studies on manganese lump ores have observed a deviation between the programmed and achieved temperatures during the experiments. The temperature increase is higher for MnO₂ containing ores compared to Mn₂O₃ containing ores which can be explained by the additional exothermic chemical reaction taking place in the former case (reaction (3)) [3,18]. During isothermal reduction of a Mn₂O₃ containing ore, a temperature increase around 60-80 °C occurred after the introduction of H₂ [20].

The reduction of manganese ores with H₂ has been studied both using finely ground samples smaller than 1 mm [21–23,26] and using lumpy ores and pellets in the mm-cm range [1,13,14,20,27,28]. The effect of reduction rate on particle size has previously been investigated during reduction in CO/CO₂ gas mixtures, and it was found through kinetic modeling that the reaction rate was proportional to the inverse mean particle size [16]. However, to the author's knowledge, no investigations on the effect of particle size on reduction of manganese lump ores with H₂ have been conducted. Acquiring knowledge on the effects of changing particle size on the reduction of manganese ores with H₂ is important to give insight into design, operation and industrialization of hydrogen reduction reactors.

Manganese ores are also known to decrepitate during heating and reduction. Phase changes during reduction of oxides and decomposition of carbonates and structural water may introduce internal stresses that contribute to the decrepitation of the material [29–31].

In this work, the reduction of Nchwanning ore with H₂ is investigated under isothermal and non-isothermal conditions, with different initial particle size distributions to investigate the effect of varying the particle size on reduction and decrepitation.

2. Materials and method

2.1. Raw materials

Table 1: Selected components from chemical analysis [13].

Component	[%]
Mn _{tot}	45.4

Fe _{tot}	9.9
CO ₂	4.5

Nchwaning manganese ore was used for the experiments. The ore contains mostly Mn₂O₃ type oxides (bixbyite, braunite I and braunite II), some hausmannite (Mn₃O₄) and hematite (Fe₂O₃), in addition to calcite (CaCO₃) and other minor phases [4,10,13]. The unreduced ore was previously analyzed [13], and selected results are given in table 1.

Table 2: Theoretical weight loss calculated from the different contributions.

Reaction	Weightloss [%]
$Mn_2O_3 \rightarrow MnO$	6.61
$Fe_2O_3 \rightarrow FeO$	1.42
$FeO \rightarrow Fe$	2.83
$CaCO_3 \rightarrow CaO + CO_2$	4.50
Sum (MnO-FeO)	12.53
Sum (MnO-Fe)	15.37

If all Mn in the ore is Mn₂O₃, Fe is Fe₂O₃ and all CO₂ originates from CaCO₃, the ore consists of 65.2 % Mn₂O₃, 14.2 % Fe₂O₃, 10.2 % CaCO₃ as well as 10.4 % other minerals. The theoretical weight loss from reduction and decomposition based on these assumptions are given in table 2.

Two different particle size distributions were investigated: 8-14 mm and 14-25 mm. Each particle size distribution was split, and 1 kg of each of the narrower particle size distributions were mixed and added according to table 3.

Table 3: Input particle size distributions

Particle size distribution	8 - 14 mm	14 - 25 mm
1kg	8 - 11.2 mm	14 - 20 mm
1kg	11.2 - 14mm	20 - 25 mm

2.2. Experimental setup

The experiments were run in a resistance heated furnace in a Kanthal® crucible with the gas inlet in the bottom and outlet with gas analysis at the top, as indicated in figure 1a. The crucible lid has two openings, one in the center and one in the edge. When adding the sample to the crucible, two thermocouples are placed in the sample, with the tip height position in the middle of the sample, 5.5 cm above the bottom of the crucible. One thermocouple is in the center of the crucible and the other is close to the crucible wall, as indicated in figure 1a. The furnace has a separate thermocouple for temperature control, located outside the crucible.

To control the gas addition, separate mass flow controllers (Alicat Scientific, USA) are used for each gas. The gases are mixed prior to entering the furnace. The utilized gases were 99.999 % Ar, 99.999 % N₂ and 99.995 % H₂. The furnace and mass flow controllers are controlled by a computer program which logs the measured temperatures and gas flow every 5 seconds.

Fig. 1: The temperature programs for the experiments. (Figure 1(a): reproduced with permission from T. Aarnæs)

Isothermal and non-isothermal experiments were conducted with a reducing gas containing 90 % H₂ and 10 % N₂. In the isothermal experiments, the crucible was heated to the chosen temperature and held for 60 minutes under argon flow to allow the temperature of the ore to approach the isothermal temperature. After the 60 min holding time, the reducing gas mixture (90 % H₂ and 10 % N₂) was introduced with a reduction time of 120 minutes. In the non-isothermal experiments, the crucible was heated with a heating rate of 5 °C/min up to 800 °C under constant flow of the reducing gas mixture. Figure 1b shows the temperature programs for the different experiments. The reducing gas mixture was introduced at time = 0 min, and the crucible was flushed with argon during the cooling period.

The off-gas was analyzed with an Agilent 490-PRO Micro-GC using ProStation analysis-software. The instrument was equipped with two analysis columns and thermal conductivity detectors (TCD). The GC method was developed based on Agilent Application notes 5991-6241 EN, 5994-0040 EN, and 5991-3364 EN. The 10 m Molsieve 5Å column of GC-Channel 1 was operated with Argon as carrier gas at 22 PSI and 110 °C. The injector was kept at 85 °C and injection time was set to 50 msec. Channel 1 was back-flashed after 8 sec. GC-Channel 2 was equipped with a 10 m PPQ column operated at 70°C with Helium as carrier gas at 22 PSI. The injector temperature was set to 85 °C. An external sample pump extracted a sample gas flow from the process gas at the rate of 50 ml/min from the total process gas leaving the furnace. This sample gas flow was filtered and cooled to remove dust and water prior to the analysis. The content of H₂, N₂, CO and CO₂ were continuously measured throughout the reduction time of the experiments.

An example of the result from the GC measurements is given in figure 2a. H₂O condenses prior to the analysis and cannot be measured in the current setup. In order to quantify the components of the off-gas, 10 % N₂ was added as a tracer gas. The quantity of the remaining gases can then be calculated based on their relative composition compared to the analyzed N₂. The volume flow \dot{V}_i^{out} of CO, CO₂ and H₂ from the crucible is calculated according to equation 6 where $\%_i^{out}$ is the measured composition of the species in the off-gas, %

N_2^{out} is the measured N_2 in the off-gas and $\dot{V}_{N_2}^{in}$ is the input volume flow of N_2 .

$$\dot{V}_i^{out} = \frac{\%i^{out}}{\%N_2^{out}} \dot{V}_{N_2}^{in} \quad i = CO, CO_2, H_2 \quad (6)$$

The water content can then be calculated based on the consumed H_2 since each consumed H_2 molecule produces one water molecule. Assuming ideal gas, the molar volume remains constant and the molar balance can be translated directly into a volume balance as shown in equation 7, where $\dot{V}_{H_2O}^{Produced}$ is the H_2O flow and $\dot{V}_{H_2}^{In}$ is the input H_2 to the crucible.

$$\dot{V}_{H_2O}^{Produced} = \dot{V}_{H_2}^{In} - \dot{V}_{H_2}^{out} \quad (7)$$

The H_2 concentrations were high compared to the GC calibration. To compensate for this, the initial parts of the non-isothermal experiments, where no reduction occurs, were used as a reference to correct the H_2 content. Figure 2b shows the corrected gas composition of the gas exiting the crucible, where the H_2O content is calculated from the consumption of H_2 .

Fig. 2: The (a): measured off gas composition and the (b): calculated off-gas composition from the furnace.

On a few occasions, the GC measurement had to be aborted due to accumulation of water in the sampling system. One of these experiments was rerun and the GC results from the two parallel experiments are compared in figure 3. It can be seen that the off-gas behavior of the two parallel experiments is similar, indicating a reasonable reproducibility of the experiments.

Fig. 3: The off-gas measurements from two parallel experiments, one where the GC measurements were interrupted before the conclusion of the experiment.

After every experiment, the material was cooled in the crucible in argon atmosphere to prevent re-oxidation. Each sample was weighed, and hand sieved to prevent additional decrepitation. A riffle splitter was used to split each sample twice, and $\frac{1}{4}$ of the sample was milled in a ring mill (Retsch RS200). The milled sample was split 2-3 more times to produce sample sizes fit for XRF, XRD and total oxygen analysis.

2.3 Chemical analysis

The chemical composition (XRF) of the samples was measured by a PANalytical Zetium 4 kW X-ray spectrometer using the fused bead technique. The total oxygen content of the samples was measured with a Leco ONH836 instrument (inert gas fusion technique). X-ray diffraction (XRD) was recorded using a Bruker D8 A25 DaVinci X-ray Diffractometer with Cu-K α radiation and a LynxEye SuperSpeed detector. Phases were identified using the Bruker Diffrac.EVA software in conjunction with the ICDD PDF5+ database (2023) and Crystallographic Open Database. Rietveld type fitting was performed using the Bruker Topas v6 software.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Reduction in fixed bed

Fig. 4: The (a): calculated off gas composition and (b): the control temperature and measured charge temperatures for the non-isothermal experiments.

The removal of oxygen from the manganese and iron oxides in the ore is calculated based on recorded hydrogen consumption during temperature ramping and holding time. From the reduction curves for non-isothermal reduction as shown in figure 4a, it becomes evident that reduction initiates after about 70 min, corresponding to a furnace temperature of 370 °C. The sample with smaller particles in the range between 8 to 14 mm has a consistently higher hydrogen conversion compared to the sample with larger particle in range of 14-25 mm. The rate of hydrogen conversion peaks around 100 min ($T_{\text{furnace}} = 520$ °C) and coincides with increased charge temperatures compared to the temperature program (figure 4b), which may be explained by the increased extent of exothermal reduction reactions.

A secondary peak in hydrogen consumption is observed around 140 minutes, where the furnace temperature is about 720 °C. This secondary peak correlates with the decomposition of carbonates, as observed by the measured CO and CO₂ in the off-gas. The carbonate decomposition is seen to initiate around 120 minutes, where the furnace

temperature is about 620 °C. At the end of the experiment, it can be seen that the H₂O content is around 20 % for both experiments, indicating that the samples are not fully reduced. Similarly, it can be seen that there is still CO and CO₂ in the off-gas, indicating that the carbonate decomposition is incomplete at the conclusion of the isothermal experiments.

Fig. 5: The calculated off gas composition from the isothermal experiments at (a): 700 °C and (b): 800 °C. The off-gas measurement in the 800 °C - 8-14 mm experiment had to be interrupted prior to the completion of the experiment due to accumulation of water in the sampling system.

Figure 5 shows the off-gas composition from the isothermal experiments. The off-gas measurements on the smaller particle size of the 800 °C experiment was interrupted due to accumulation of water in the sampling system; nevertheless, the experiment was run to completion without off-gas analysis. The hydrogen consumption was higher for the smaller particle size distribution for both temperatures. Carbonates decomposed right after injection of hydrogen gas and most of the carbonates were decomposed within 30 minutes of the experiment's isothermal holding time.

The CO₂ from decomposition of carbonates will react with H₂ according to the water–gas shift reaction (WGSR) ($\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO} = \text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_2$) [1,3], which can be observed by the measured CO in the experiments. Hence, the secondary peak in H₂ consumption is a combination of oxide reduction and CO₂ conversion. During the reduction of Nchwaning ore in CO/CO₂ gas mixtures [18], carbonates were seen to decompose close to 900 °C. This inhibiting effect of CO₂ gas on the carbonate decomposition was also observed during reduction of UMK ore [1], where about 50 % of the carbonates remained in the ore after reduction at 800 °C in CO/CO₂. The carbonates were however fully decomposed after reduction at 700 °C in H₂ and H₂/H₂O atmospheres, which is consistent with the observations in this work. Neither the presence of H₂O nor H₂ will inhibit the carbonate decomposition reaction, however the relative content of the two gases will influence the equilibrium composition of the WGSR. At the beginning of the H₂ injection during the isothermal experiments, the oxide reduction rate is high, thus, H₂ gas is consumed and the concentration of water vapor in the furnace atmosphere is high. In figure 5 it can be seen that the H₂O content is above 60 % at the start of the isothermal experiments and remains above 40 % for most of the time where the carbonates decompose. Conversely, at the point with highest carbonate decomposition in the non-isothermal experiments (figure 4), the H₂O content is between 20 % and 30 %. The opposite behavior can be observed for the H₂ content in both cases. Considering the equilibrium of the WGSR ($\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO} = \text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_2$), a higher H₂ content and a lower H₂O content of the gas phase is expected to shift the equation to the left. The equilibrium composition of two gas mixtures was calculated and is given in table 4. Assuming an input

composition of 5 % CO₂ and 0 % CO with, respectively, 60 % and 20 % H₂O (Balance H₂), a significant difference in the equilibrium CO content can be observed; 52 % of the CO₂ is converted to CO when the input gas contains 60 % H₂O and 92 % of the CO₂ is converted when the input gas contains 20 % H₂O.

Table 4: Input and equilibrium composition assuming the equilibrium of the water-gas shift reaction at 700 °C. Calculated using HSC Chemistry 10®.

Gas composition	CO ₂ [%]	CO [%]	H ₂ O [%]	H ₂ [%]
Input	5	0	60	35
Equilibrium	2.4	2.6	62.6	32.4
Input	5	0	20	75
Equilibrium	0.4	4.6	24.6	70.4

It is worth noticing that the conversion rate in the isothermal experiments is high in the beginning and reaction slows down due to the depletion of oxides. The high conversion rate is also observed by the increased sample temperature due to the exothermal reduction reactions between manganese oxides and H₂, an example of which is shown in Fig 6. At the end of the isothermal experiments, the H₂O content is significantly lower compared to the non-isothermal experiments, indicating that the reduction is closer to completion in the isothermal experiments. The reduction of manganese oxides starts at lower temperatures in the non-isothermal experiments, however, the sample spends significantly less time at high temperatures in these experiments. For comparison, the sample in the non-isothermal experiment spent about 20 minutes above 700 °C, as compared to 120 minutes at 700 °C and 800 °C, respectively, in the isothermal experiments.

Fig. 6: The off-gas composition and measured temperature from a 14-25 mm sample reduced isothermally at 800 °C.

The chemical analysis of the reduced samples is given in table 5. The O/Mn ratio of all heat-treated samples indicates that the manganese is fully reduced to MnO except for the 14-25 mm sample non-isothermally. This sample contains a small amount of excess oxygen compared to the manganese content, also reflected in the total oxygen measurement, which is the highest among the isothermally reduced samples. The total oxygen measurement of the non-isothermally reduced samples (non-iso) was higher than in the samples which were reduced isothermally (iso).

One contribution to the higher total oxygen measurements (in the non-iso samples) is the remaining carbonates in the sample. The total oxygen is measured by quantifying the CO and CO₂ in the off-gas after the oxygen in the sample has reacted with carbon. As such, decomposing carbonates will be interpreted as oxygen content in the

total oxygen measurement. Higher oxygen content in the iron oxides would also contribute to the increased oxygen measurement. Iron oxides are more difficult to reduce compared to manganese oxides of the same oxidation state, and since the non-isothermally reduced samples spent a short time at high temperatures (about 20 minutes above 700 °C), it is reasonable to assume that the iron oxides in these samples contribute to the higher oxygen content compared to the isothermally reduced samples.

Table 5: Chemical composition of reduced samples

Iso/non-iso		Iso ^{&}	iso	iso	iso	non-iso	non-iso
T	[°C]	700	800	700	800	0-800	0-800
dp	[mm]	8-14	8-14	14-25	14-25	8-14	14-25
Mn	[%]	51.2	50.6	52.2	50.7	50.5	52.1
Fe	[%]	11.3	12.4	11.7	12.4	12.0	10.5
Mn/Fe	-	4.5	4.1	4.5	4.1	4.2	5.0
K ₂ O	[%]	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.04
MgO	[%]	1.5	1.7	1.4	1.4	1.8	1.7
S	[%]	0.21	0.18	0.44	0.22	0.18	0.23
P	[%]	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04
SiO ₂	[%]	3.3	3.6	3.1	3.3	3.5	3.6
TiO ₂	[%]	0	0	0	0	0	0
Al ₂ O ₃	[%]	0	0	0	0.42	0	0
CaO	[%]	8.1	7.5	7.0	7.1	7.8	7.9
BaO	[%]	0.68	0.49	0.60	0.79	0.60	0.64
LOI 950*	[%]	-7.4	-8.8	-6.2	-7.5	-4.1	-7.5
O/Mn [‡]	mol/mol	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.05
Total O [#]	[%]	22.9	22.3	24.4	22.9	24.5	25.9

[&]Sample with shorter soaking time, ^{*}Stable weight after treatment at 950 °C, [‡]Titrimetric measurement, [#]Total oxygen (Leco)

Fig. 7: The measured weight loss for experiments at different conditions. (a): the weight loss as a function of temperature and (b): the weight loss as a function of measured total oxygen content. *marks references of unreduced and fully reduced ore from a different setup [13]. The theoretical weight loss for reduction to MnO-FeO and MnO-Fe is indicated on the figure.

The weight of the samples was measured before and after the experiments. The overall weight loss of the reduced samples is given in figure 7a. Reference samples of fully reduced and unreduced samples were also included for comparison. The reduced reference sample was reduced in pure H₂ at 900 °C in a different setup [13] and achieved

a reduction similar to the theoretical reduction, i.e. all carbonates were decomposed, all iron oxides were reduced to metallic iron and all manganese oxides were reduced to MnO. The weight loss of the 8-14 mm particles was higher compared to the 14-25 mm particles run at similar conditions. The non-isothermal experiments display a lower weight loss compared to the isothermal experiments, which correlates with the higher total oxygen in the samples (table 5). This is also supported by the observations in figure 4, where it was observed that neither the oxide reduction nor the carbonate decomposition was completed at the conclusion of the experiment. The 14-25 mm sample reduced non-isothermally was the only sample where higher manganese oxides were detected by the titrimetric analysis and is also the sample with the highest total oxygen content.

Increasing the temperature results in an increased weight loss, and the weight loss for the isothermally reduced samples indicates a composition between MnO-FeO and MnO-Fe. In figure 7b, the measured weight loss is compared to the measured total oxygen. The graph shows a good correlation between the two parameters. Furthermore, the total oxygen is always higher in the samples that contain coarser particle sizes compared to samples with finer grains run at similar conditions.

The XRD analysis results are listed in Table 5. The "MnO" phase was identified as mainly MnO, however variations in the unit cell parameter and asymmetric peaks indicated that the MnO phase also contained other cations such as Fe, Ca and Mg. The dissolution of these cations in the MnO phase has also been reported in other investigation [1,32–34]. Portlandite was identified in all samples even though it is not thermodynamically stable above 518 °C. During cooling after the experiment, Argon is flushed through the setup, however it is possible that some water vapor was still present in the crucible as the ore was cooled below 518 °C and reacted with the CaO from carbonate decomposition. Another option is that the portlandite was formed by the reaction between CaO and atmospheric moisture during sample storage between the experiment and the analysis. The effect of mass addition due to the reaction between CaO and H₂O to produce portlandite can be found by the molar weight ratio between CaO and portlandite. The samples contained 1.5–5.7 %, portlandite, which introduces an uncertainty in the measured weight of 0.4-1.4 % in the measured weight of the samples depending on when the portlandite was formed. Upon implementation in an industrial system, any portlandite produced would have to be calcined in the subsequent step, causing a slight increase in energy consumption.

The chemical analysis of the non-isothermal experiments (table 5) indicates that the manganese oxides are fully reduced to MnO for all the samples except the coarse particle size fraction reduced non-isothermally. However, since higher manganese oxides are identified in the XRD analysis for most samples, it is apparent that the resolution of the titrimetric determination of the O/Mn ratio is not sufficient to identify the remaining Mn³⁺ in bixbyite when the content is 5.6 % or lower.

The XRD results, given in figure 8 and table 6, confirm the observations from the total oxygen measurements and weight loss and aligns well in comparison to the theoretical phase composition (figure 7). It is seen that the incomplete reduction according to the weight loss is caused by the incomplete reduction of oxides and decomposition of carbonates. The higher bixbyite-, lower MnO- and higher carbonate content in the non-isothermally reduced samples confirm the previous observations that the samples are less reduced compared to the isothermally reduced samples. For the isothermally reduced samples, the metallic iron content is higher for samples reduced at higher temperatures and for the smaller particle size distribution. The higher metallic iron content and reduced content of higher oxides in the smaller particles indicates a higher reaction rate of the smaller particles since all experiments were done for the same length of time. The reactant and product gases have longer

diffusion paths in the larger particles compared to the smaller ones.

Fig. 8: X-ray diffraction patterns and identified phases for the reduced samples.

The bixbyite content shows the opposite trend compared to the metallic iron; the least reduced sample was the one with coarsest particle size distribution at the lowest temperature, while increasing the reduction temperature or reducing the particle size distribution increases the reduction degree of the samples. Most of the manganese is converted to MnO, while a minor amount remains in the bixbyite. The unreduced iron report to the bixbyite and brownmillerite phases.

Table 6: Results from Rietveld refinement of XRD data. The “MnO” phase also contains cations like Fe, Mg and Ca.

Iso/non-iso			iso*	iso	iso	iso	non-iso	non-iso
T		[°C]	700	800	700	800	0-800	0-800
d _p		[mm]	8-14	8-14	14-25	14-25	8-14	14-25
"MnO"	MnO	[%]	90	90	90	91	83	80
Iron	Fe	[%]	4.7	5.9	1.6	3.4	0.4	0.2
Bixbyite	FeMnO ₃	[%]	1.7	-	2.2	1.4	5.6	10.2
Brownmillerite	Ca ₂ FeAlO ₅	[%]	1.5	1.6	2.3	1.8	0.9	2.9
Calcite	CaCO ₃	[%]	-	-	1.0	-	4.3	5.1
Portlandite	Ca(OH) ₂	[%]	2.6	2.3	3.3	2.5	5.7	1.5

*Average of two samples

3.2. Decrepitation

The samples were sieved after reduction to determine the decrepitation of the material. Figure 9 shows the particle size distribution before and after the experiments. For easier comparison, the amount material passing through the 6.7 mm sieve is given in figure 10. Two parallel experiments were conducted for the 14-25 mm fraction at 700 °C, and the results from both experiments were included in figure 9b and figure 10.

Fig. 9: The particle size distribution before and after reduction for the (a): 8-14 mm and (b): 14-25 mm particles. Two experiments were conducted isothermally at 700 °C as seen in (b).

Fig. 10: The weight [%] of the reduced samples passing through a 6.7 mm sieve. Two experiments were conducted isothermally at 700 °C.

For both of the initial particle size distributions, the material is seen to decrepitate the most after isothermal reduction at 700 °C, whereas isothermal reduction at 800 °C produces the least amount of fines. In previous investigations the decrepitation has been seen to increase with increasing temperature [29–31], which is inconsistent with the observations in this work. In a previous investigation on the same ore [13], BET measurements and SEM investigations indicated sintering in the microstructure after reduction at 800 °C, which was not observed after reduction at 700 °C. Sintering of the material might increase its mechanical strength, resulting in less breakages of the material during handling and sieving after reduction, explaining the decrease in decrepitation during the increased reduction temperature.

4. Conclusions

Two particle size distributions of Nchwaning manganese ore were reduced in a 90 % H₂ – 10 % N₂ atmosphere, under isothermal conditions at 700 °C and 800 °C, as well as non-isothermally up to 800 °C with 5 °C/min heating rate.

The results show that particle size has a significant influence on the reduction rate. Manganese is reduced to MnO more rapidly the smaller the particles. Off gas analysis indicates that reduction of metal oxides was still occurring after 120 minutes of exposure to hydrogen at temperatures between 700 - 800 °C. Compared to change

in particle size distribution, the temperature increase from 700 - 800 °C did not have a pronounced effect on the reduction rate.

The off-gas analysis indicated that the non-isothermally reduced samples were less reduced and retained a higher carbonate content compared to the isothermally reduced samples, which was confirmed by the subsequent analysis.

The manganese oxides in isothermally reduced samples were close to fully reduced to MnO, with 0-2.2 % remaining bixbyite as identified by XRD. A significant fraction of iron was reduced to its metallic form, while some remained as oxides in the bixbyite and brownmillerite phases. Increased temperature and decreasing particle size distribution improves the degree of reduction of the ore.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

- [1] J. Davies, M. Tangstad, T. L. Schanche, S. P. du Preez, Pre-Reduction of United Manganese of Kalahari Ore in CO/CO₂, H₂/H₂O, and H₂ Atmospheres, *Metall Mater Trans B*, 54, (2023), No. 2, p. 515–535.
- [2] M. Tangstad, T. Schanche, F. de Preez, Use of H₂ in Mn-Ferroalloy Production, *Advances in Pyrometallurgy*, (2023), p. 35–53.
- [3] T. A. Larssen, M. Tangstad, Effect of Moisture, Hydrogen, and Water–Gas Shift Reaction on the Prereduction Behavior of Comilog and Nchwaning Manganese Ores, *Metall Mater Trans B*, 53, (2022), No. 4, p. 2104–2116.
- [4] T. L. Schanche, M. Tangstad, Prereduction of Nchwaning Ore in CO/CO₂/H₂ Gas Mixtures, *Minerals*, 11, (2021), No. 10, p. 1097.
- [5] D. Ngoy, D. Sukhomlinov, M. Tangstad, Pre-Reduction Behaviour of Manganese Ores in H₂ and CO Containing Gases, *ISIJ International*, 60, (2020), No. 11, p. 2325–2331.
- [6] C. van der Eijk, H. Dalaker, J. Safarian, Possibilities and Limitations of the Use of Hydrogen in Different Metallurgical Sectors, *Materials Proceedings*, 15, (2023), No. 1, p. 63.
- [7] A. S. Akhmetov, Zh. V. Ereemeeva, E. N. Makhambetov, Application of Hydrogen in Production of Ferroalloys, *Metallurgist*, 67, (2024), No. 11, p. 1621–1627.
- [8] I. T. Kero, H. Dalaker, K. Sende Osen, E. Ringdalen, Some Carbon-Free Technologies for Manganese Ferroalloy Production, *Proceedings of the 16th International Ferro-Alloys Congress (INFACON XVI)*, (2021), p. 9.
- [9] J. Safarian, A Sustainable Process to Produce Manganese and Its Alloys through Hydrogen and Aluminothermic Reduction, *Processes*, 10, (2022), No. 1, p. 27.
- [10] T. A. Larssen, D. Senk, M. Tangstad, Reduction of Manganese Ores in CO-CO₂ Atmospheres, *Metall Mater Trans B*, 52, (2020), No. 1, p. 363–381.
- [11] A. Cheraghi, H. Becker, H. Eftekhari, H. Yoozbashizadeh, J. Safarian, Characterization and Calcination Behavior of a Low-Grade Manganese Ore, *Materials Today Communications*, 25, (2020), p. 101382.
- [12] M. S. Fahim, H. El Faramawy, A. M. Ahmed, S. N. Ghali, A. E. H. T. Kandil, Characterization of Egyptian Manganese Ores for Production of High Carbon Ferromanganese, *Journal of Minerals and Materials Characterization and Engineering*, 01, (2013), No. 02, p. 68–74.
- [13] A. Sarkar, T. L. Schanche, J. Safarian, Isothermal Pre-Reduction Behavior of Nchwaning Manganese Ore in H₂ Atmosphere, *Materials Proceedings*, 15, (2023), No. 1, p. 58.
- [14] M. S. Ernst, M. Tangstad, S. P. Du Preez, Pre-Reduction of Nchwaning Manganese Ore in CO/CO₂, H₂/H₂O, and H₂ Atmospheres, *Minerals Engineering*, 216, (2024), p. 108854.

- [15] K. L. Berg, S. E. Olsen, Kinetics of Manganese Ore Reduction by Carbon Monoxide, *Metall and Materi Trans B*, 31, (2000), No. 3, p. 477–490.
- [16] T. A. Larssen, D. Senk, M. Tangstad, Reaction Rate Analysis of Manganese Ore Prereduction in CO-CO₂ Atmosphere, *Metall Mater Trans B*, 52, (2021), No. 4, p. 2087–2100.
- [17] Y. B. Gao, H. G. Kim, H. Y. Sohn, Kinetics of Pre-Reduction of Manganese Ore by CO, *Mineral Processing & Extractive Metallurgy: Transactions of the Institution of Mining & Metallurgy, Section C*, 121, (2012), No. 2, p. 109–116.
- [18] T. Mukono, H. S. Reiersen, T. L. Schanche, M. Wallin, M. Tangstad, Prereduction Behavior of Manganese Ores With Solid Carbon and in CO/CO₂ Gas Atmosphere, *Metall Mater Trans B*, 53, (2022), No. 5, p. 3292–3305.
- [19] R. Kononov, O. Ostrovski, S. Ganguly, Carbothermal Reduction of Manganese Oxide in Different Gas Atmospheres, *Metall and Materi Trans B*, 39, (2008), No. 5, p. 662–668.
- [20] A. Sarkar, T. L. Schanche, M. Wallin, J. Safarian, Evaluating the Reaction Kinetics on the H₂ Reduction of a Manganese Ore at Elevated Temperatures, *J. Sustain. Metall.*, 10, (2024), No. 4, p. 2085–2103.
- [21] H. E. Barner, C. L. Mantell, Kinetics of Hydrogen Reduction of Manganese Dioxide, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Proc. Des. Dev.*, 7, (1968), No. 2, p. 285–294.
- [22] T. J. W. De Bruijn, T. H. Soerawidjaja, W. A. De Jongt, P. J. Van Den Berg, Modelling of the Reduction of Manganese Oxides with Hydrogen, *Chemical Engineering Science*, 35, (1980), No. 7, p. 1591–1599.
- [23] R. Wang, S. Yuan, Y. Li, P. Gao, R. Li, Hydrogen-Based Mineral Phase Transformation Mechanism Investigation of Pyrolusite Ore, *Int J Miner Metall Mater*, 31, (2024), No. 11, p. 2445–2457.
- [24] V. Canaguier, T. L. Schanche, T. Mukono, E. Ringdalen, Kinetic Modelling of FeMn Pilot Experiments: Investigating the Effect of Charge Type and Pre-Treatment, *Proceedings of the 62nd Conference of Metallurgists, COM 2023*, (2023), p. 651–663.
- [25] K. Turkova, D. Slizovskiy, M. Tangstad, CO Reactivity and Porosity of Manganese Materials, *ISIJ Int.*, 54, (2014), No. 6, p. 1204–1208.
- [26] M. I. Zaki, M. A. Hasan, L. Pasupulety, K. Kumari, Thermochemistry of Manganese Oxides in Reactive Gas Atmospheres: Probing Redox Compositions in the Decomposition Course MnO₂ → MnO, *Thermochimica Acta*, 303, (1997), No. 2, p. 171–181.
- [27] H. H. A. El-Gawad, M. M. Ahmed, N. A. El-Hussiny, M. E. H. Shalabi, Reduction of Low Grade Egyptian Manganese Ore via Hydrogen at 800°C - 950°C, *Open Access Library Journal*, 1, (2014), No. 4, p. 1–11.
- [28] N. El-Hussiny, H. H. Abd El-Gawad, M. F. M., M. Shalabi, Pelletization and Reduction of Egyptian Low Grade Manganese Ore Pellets via Hydrogen at 750-950°C, *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 6, (2015), No. 5, p. 339–346.
- [29] G. L. Faria, J. A. S. Tenório, N. Jannotti, F. G. da S. Araújo, Disintegration on Heating of a Brazilian Manganese Lump Ore, *International Journal of Mineral Processing*, 124, (2013), p. 132–137.
- [30] M. S. Moholwa, J. D. Steenkamp, H. L. Rutto, Fines Generation from South African Manganese Ores during Preheating in a Rotary Kiln, *J. S. Afr. Inst. Min. Metall.*, 122, (2023), No. 11, p. 1–10.
- [31] A. Biswas, P. Kr. Das, V. Singh, Investigation of the Decrepitation Phenomenon of Polymorphic Materials: A Theoretical and Experimental Study, *Powder Technology*, 294, (2016), p. 119–133.
- [32] B. Sorensen, S. Gaal, E. Ringdalen, M. Tangstad, R. Kononov, O. Ostrovski, Phase Compositions of Manganese Ores and Their Change in the Process of Calcination, *International Journal of Mineral Processing*, 94, (2010), No. 3, p. 101–110.
- [33] T. Coetsee, The Role of Manganese Ore Reduction Morphology Development in Setting Reduction Mechanisms, *Minerals Engineering*, 137, (2019), p. 217–231.
- [34] B. Liu, Y. Zhang, J. Wang, J. Wang, Z. Su, G. Li, T. Jiang, A Further Investigation on the MnO₂-Fe₂O₃ System Roasted under CO-CO₂ Atmosphere, *Advanced Powder Technology*, 30, (2019), No. 2, p. 302–310.